

FAAM facility for airborne atmospheric measurements

FLIGHT FOLDER

Flight No.: B298
Date: 22 June 2007
Take Off: 17:08:51
Landing: 20:28:59
Flight Time: 3h 20m 08s

Campaign: GERBIL

Operating Area: Dakar - Niamey

POB	Position	Name	Institute
1	Captain	Alan Roberts	Directflight
2	Co-pilot	Alan Foster	Directflight
3	CCM1	Jackie Mulholland	Directflight
4	CCM2	Dawn Quinn	Directflight
5	Core Chem.	Kate Turnbull	FAAM
6	Flight Manager	Jim Crawford	FAAM
7	Mission Scientist 1	Jim Haywood	Met Office
8	Mission Scientist 2	Ben Johnson	Met Office
9	AVAPS	Doug Anderson	FAAM
10	Filters	Paula Formenti	University of Paris 12 (LISA)
11	ARIES	Stuart Rogers	Met Office
12	Neph / PSAP / SWS	Andy Wilson	Met Office
13	Cloud Physics	Martyn Pickering	Met Office
14	Mission Scientist 3	John Marsham	Leeds University

Flight Track:

B298 Track 22-JUN-07

FLIGHT SUMMARY

Flight No B298

Date: 22 Jun 2007

Project: GERBIL

Location: Land areas between Dakar and Niamey - direct line as mostly a transit flight.

Start Time	End Time	Event	Height (s)	Hdg	Comments
----	----	-----	-----	---	-----
165315		CGPS	0.20 kft	335	B298cgps.log
165404		INU	0.20 kft	335	to navigate
165523		GIN	0.20 kft	335	on
170851		T/O	0.21 kft	354	Dakar
170910	173547	Profile 1	0.42 - 25.0 kft	004	start at t/o
170938		heimann	0.86 kft	071	open
171056		Video	2.1 kft	095	#1 ffc, #2 dfc start
171119		psap	2.6 kft	094	flow on at t/o
173548	195445	Run 1.1	25.0 - 29.0 kft	089	
173623		bbr	25.0 kft	089	retract
173803		Heimann	25.0 kft	091	cal 12
183058		r1.1	25.5 kft	091	cruise climb to fl270
183917		!	27.0 kft	092	level 270
184332		Video	27.0 kft	091	#1, #2 end. #3ffc, #4 dfc start
184737		psap	28.9 kft	091	flow off, entering cloud
185518		!	29.0 kft	092	temp -29, dewpoint-28
185537		!	29.0 kft	092	rosemount deice on
185639		heimann	29.0 kft	092	cal 06
190304		!	29.0 kft	092	rosemount deice off
190539		psap	29.0 kft	092	flow on
193420		Video	29.0 kft	102	end recording
195445	202938	Profile 2	29.0 - 0.84 kft	100	at land
195804		bbr	26.4 kft	102	retract
200854		psap	15.3 kft	097	flow on
202645		bbr	2.1 kft	010	retract
202716		heimann	1.7 kft	319	closed
202859		Land	0.81 kft	264	Niamey
203441		Shutdown	0.84 kft	102	

B298 Track 22-JUN-07

FAAM Sortie Brief

Gerbils: Geostationary Earth Radiation Budget Intercomparison of Longwave and Shortwave radiation.

Flight No: B297b

Date: 22nd June 2007

Trial objectives:

To carry out remote sensing measurements between Nouakchott to Niamey.

Location:

Over land areas between Nouakchott and Niamey.

Weather:

Clear skies preferred.

Special requirements:

Instruments of particular importance:

Nephelometer/wet-nephelometer combination

PCASP

PSAP

BBRs

SWS/SHIMS

ARIES

Flight pattern:

1. If cloud-free, perform a pirouette.
2. Take off from Nouakchott at 16:00Z.
3. Perform a profile ascent towards Nouakchott at 1000ft/min to FL240 (25mins).
4. Perform a SLR at FL240 towards Niamey launching sondes when requested (140mins, T=165mins).
5. Perform a profile descent and land in Niamey (25mins, T=190mins).
6. If cloud-free, perform a pirouette on landing.

Sortie Debrief

Flight Number: B298

Date: 22nd June 2007

Sortie Objectives: To investigate the in-situ and radiative effects of dust storms in conjunction with the GERB/SEVIRI satellite instruments.

Operating area: Land areas between Dakar and Niamey – direct line as mostly a transit flight.

Weather: Hazy conditions with significant dust as the western points. Some Cb activity to the south of the easternmost point. Lots of cloud at variable heights.

Flight Patterns: Subsequent to take-off, a profile ascent was performed to FL240 (above the dust layer) above the dust layer. A long SLR was then performed at this altitude (and on occasion to FL260) to Niamey. Initially there was no cloud for the first 20 minutes of the flight, but subsequently there was plenty of cloud from the top of the dust layer at FL180 to FL260. A profile descent was then performed to land at Niamey.

Summary: Essentially a transit flight, but use could be made of the profile ascent from Dakar and the profile descent into Niamey.

Problems:

PCASP U/S – it was later found that the motor had failed.

CO shows some unusual profiles which warrants further investigation.

BBRs showed non-negligible fluxes when it was dark – warrants further investigation.

Jim Haywood

Mission Scientist's Log

Dakar → Niamey

Flight No **B.298** Date 22nd June 07 Name ~~Jim Haywood~~ Page 2 of 3
Jh Masqam

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
19:00:00					Log resumed
					Post and remain / Cb
					Gr, was I detected cloud?
					Always mixed-phase ~ -25°C?
					Multiple layers class level
					CI ballstak above
19:06:19		29000'		16°30'N 5°18'W	7/8 Al Cu ~ 3000' below CI to left ~ 29000'
19:10:18					Al Cu layer up to 5000' & Guas in cloud.
19:16:00					Lower pyrogeometric data drop - - otherwise.
19:17:23					Current
19:16:20					ETA 20:20
19:23:66					Variable Al Cu below still
19:26:60					Too dark to see data below
19:37:69					Cb reported 10' of Niamey by Arrair Met. → all level clouds
19:48:45		29000' / 316 hPa			Lightly visible → on radar 30° N. of heading, heading = 101°
19:54:60 PZ		29000' ↓			Descent profile to Niamey

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No **B** 298 Date 22/6/07 Name John Masham Page 3 of 3

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
19:56:16	P2				
19:59:10					Small storm visible on aircraft radar? To Manual radar.
					Shows more Cl.
					Cl 940m → 8000m Niamey
					SE of Niamey
					Aircraft radar 20 miles ahead Cl Niamey 40 miles ahead of aircraft.
20:05:12					Radar:
20:06:14		18k' ↓			Lightning ahead, Neph $\leq 3m^{-1}$
		15.6k'			Neph has thin dust layer. 50m ⁻¹ undetermined
20:11		12800'			Pilot: vis reduced
		13000'			Neph peak at 130 m ⁻¹

Mission Scientist's Log

GERBIL

Science/Transit

Dakar → Niamey.

Flight No **B.298** Date 22nd June 07 Name Jim Heywood Page 1 of 3

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
					Dusty No cloud visible.
17:08:51	Start PI	T/O ↑			Start profile. Hazy from take-off alot of dust visually. Fire on LHS visible after take-off.
					Neph 20 15 10 5 75 200 × 10 ⁻⁶
					Out of top of dust at FL200.
17:35:49	End PI SR11	FL250			Dusty below → no cloud below during the profile PI.

CORE CHEMISTRY FLIGHT LOG FOR FLIGHT FOLDER

Flight Number : B298

Date : 22/06/07

Operator and contact info : Kate Turnbull katet@faam.ac.uk

Problems with Instruments

CO	Leak to cabin air. Data incorrect.
O₃	Lamp B overheated – cabin too hot, air conditioning increased and instrument restarted in time for last profile descent.
NO_x	Instrument cooler struggled to maintain chamber temperature – concurrent with Ozone problems.
TDLAS	None

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG Flight B 298

Date: 22/06/07 **Operator:** MAP **DRS Time:** 16:30:00 **DAU1 Time:** +0 **DAU2 Time:** +0 **DAU3 Time:** +0 **Aux1 Time:** +0 **Aux2 Time:** +0 **Page 1 of 2**

G.M.T	PCASP		FFSSP	SID1	SID2	2D2-C		2D2-P		CIP25			CIP100			Habit	Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block TX	Count	Count	Conc/L	Max size	Conc/m3	Max size	Conc m3	Max size	LWC	Conc m3	Max size	LWC		
17:09:00	Motor	Fail	?													Start Profile from takeoff	
17:11:50				20	1											FL030	
17:12:46				20	3											FL040	
17:13:50				20	3											FL050	
17:14:38				20	1											FL060	
17:15:33				15	2											FL070	
17:18:08				20	2											FL080	
17:17:40				20	2											FL090	
17:18:35				30	3											FL100	
17:19:41				20	3											FL110	
17:20:34				30	4											FL120	
17:21:34				30	2											FL130	
17:22:44				20	1											FL140	
17:23:50				20	2											FL150	
17:24:55			0	20	2											FL160	
17:25:59				20	1											FL170	
17:26:56				15	1											FL180	
17:27:59				2												FL190	
17:29:00				1												FL200	
17:30:31																FL210	
17:31:45				1												FL220	
17:32:56				1												FL230	
17:34:49				1												FL240	
17:35:46																End of P1 & Start Run 1.1 @ FL250	
17:40:00				1													
17:45:00				1													
17:50:00				1													
17:55:00			1														
18:00:00				1													
18:05:00				1													
18:10:00				1													
18:15:00				1													
18:20:00				1													
18:25:00			2	3													
18:30:00			12	2	1												
18:35:00				5	1												
18:40:00			13	5	2											FL270	
18:45:00			28	200	100	100	800								8		
18:50:00			50	2	2											FL290	
18:55:00			206	100	10	1	400								10		
19:00:00			259	1	1												
19:05:00			260	1													
19:10:00				1													
19:15:00				1	1												
19:20:00				1	1												
19:25:00			261	1	1												


```

16:58:13.22 --- - - - -
16:58:13.22 --- - - - - +++ SOFTWARE START/RESTART +++
16:58:13.22 --- - - - - +++ hh:mm:ss.ff / Instr / Posn / Period /
                    tVIS/ tNIR / Comment +++
16:58:13.22 --- - - - - +++ Flight no. B298
16:58:13.22 --- - - - -
16:58:44.11 SWS - - - - Initialization: VIS OK NIR OK
16:58:46.49 USH - - - - Initialization: VIS OK NIR OK
16:58:48.45 LSH - - - - Initialization: VIS OK NIR OK
16:58:51.91 --- - - - - Reset shutters.
16:58:55.86 --- - - - - Reset shutters.
16:59:01.99 SWS - - 200 - VIS int.time changed from 10ms to 200ms.
16:59:04.17 SWS - - - 300 - NIR int.time changed from 10ms to 300ms.
16:59:06.74 USH - - 350 - VIS int.time changed from 10ms to 350ms.
16:59:09.07 USH - - - 200 - NIR int.time changed from 10ms to 200ms.
17:00:23.33 LSH - - 400 - VIS int.time changed from 10ms to 400ms.
17:00:28.01 LSH - - - 750 - NIR int.time changed from 10ms to 750ms.
17:00:33.08 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
17:00:33.09 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
17:00:33.09 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
17:00:39.26 LSH - - 750 - VIS int.time changed from 400ms to 750ms.
17:00:51.26 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
17:00:51.69 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
17:00:51.69 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
17:00:55.12 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
17:00:55.83 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
17:00:59.19 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
17:01:01.07 SWS - - - - Idling
17:01:02.83 USH - - - - Idling
17:01:04.80 LSH - - - - Idling
17:01:15.70 --- - - - - *** preflight ok
17:01:28.63 --- - - - - *** taxiing at Dakar
17:06:59.04 --- - - - - *** sws to 90aft for take off
17:07:03.76 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
17:07:03.77 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
17:07:03.77 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
17:07:10.91 USH - - 100 - VIS int.time changed from 350ms to 100ms.
17:07:14.69 USH - - - 500 - NIR int.time changed from 200ms to 500ms.
17:07:19.70 USH - - - 750 - NIR int.time changed from 500ms to 750ms.
17:07:25.64 USH - - 150 - VIS int.time changed from 100ms to 150ms.
17:07:31.40 SWS - - - 750 - NIR int.time changed from 300ms to 750ms.
17:07:36.22 SWS - - - 300 - NIR int.time changed from 750ms to 300ms.
17:07:40.76 SWS - - 100 - VIS int.time changed from 200ms to 100ms.
17:07:43.44 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
17:07:43.88 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
17:07:43.92 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
17:07:47.19 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
17:07:50.34 --- - - - - Reset shutters.
17:07:51.81 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
17:07:52.01 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
17:07:53.93 --- - - - - Reset shutters.
17:07:57.55 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
17:08:05.48 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
17:08:14.07 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
17:08:14.18 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
17:08:14.20 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
17:08:14.59 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
17:08:18.11 SWS - - - - Idling
17:08:22.20 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
17:08:22.41 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
17:10:15.87 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
17:10:24.44 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
17:10:24.54 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
17:10:24.75 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
17:10:27.88 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
17:10:32.58 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
17:10:32.77 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.

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17:10:37.63	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:10:45.57	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:10:46.04	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
17:10:51.71	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
17:11:00.96	USH	-	-	-	150	NIR int.time changed from 750ms to 150ms.
17:11:04.59	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:11:06.52	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:11:11.10	USH	-	-	-	750	NIR int.time changed from 150ms to 750ms.
17:11:16.90	SWS	6F	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 6F
17:11:21.13	SWS	-	-	200	-	VIS int.time changed from 100ms to 200ms.
17:11:25.97	SWS	-	-	-	500	NIR int.time changed from 300ms to 500ms.
17:11:29.05	SWS	-	-	-	750	NIR int.time changed from 500ms to 750ms.
17:11:34.32	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:11:34.33	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:11:34.34	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:11:42.26	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:11:42.45	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:11:42.66	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:17:01.39	---	-	-	-	-	*** in profile climb
17:27:47.61	---	-	-	-	-	*** at FL190 and nearing the top of the dust
17:29:04.33	---	-	-	-	-	*** dust top at FL200
17:29:26.31	SWS	174R	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 174R
17:29:31.48	SWS	-	-	-	500	NIR int.time changed from 750ms to 500ms.
17:29:34.38	SWS	-	-	300	-	VIS int.time changed from 200ms to 300ms.
17:29:41.61	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:29:41.85	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:29:41.98	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:29:47.48	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:29:49.55	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:29:49.78	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:35:52.18	---	-	-	-	-	*** end profile at FL250
17:36:00.81	---	-	-	-	-	*** start of run
17:36:13.10	LSH	-	-	500	-	VIS int.time changed from 750ms to 500ms.
17:36:17.30	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:36:25.23	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:44:53.56	---	-	-	-	-	*** sws to 176R
17:45:07.87	---	-	-	-	-	*** IN_S pitch 4deg
18:03:30.44	---	-	-	-	-	*** over cloud
18:24:32.31	SWS	-	-	-	750	NIR int.time changed from 500ms to 750ms.
18:24:36.43	SWS	-	-	750	-	VIS int.time changed from 300ms to 750ms.
18:24:46.59	USH	-	-	500	-	VIS int.time changed from 150ms to 500ms.
18:24:52.36	LSH	-	-	750	-	VIS int.time changed from 500ms to 750ms.
18:24:56.97	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
18:24:56.99	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
18:24:57.25	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
18:25:04.90	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
18:25:05.14	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
18:25:05.30	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
18:26:54.34	SWS	-	-	400	-	VIS int.time changed from 750ms to 400ms.
18:26:58.67	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
18:27:06.61	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
18:29:59.10	---	-	-	-	-	*** Alto Cu below
18:30:40.12	LSH	-	-	500	-	VIS int.time changed from 750ms to 500ms.
18:30:43.96	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
18:30:51.91	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
18:31:12.58	SWS	-	-	300	-	VIS int.time changed from 400ms to 300ms.
18:31:16.11	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
18:31:24.05	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
18:35:23.21	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
18:35:31.15	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
19:01:41.98	---	-	-	-	-	*** too dark now for any useful SWS SHIMS data
19:01:48.32	SWS	-	-	750	-	VIS int.time changed from 300ms to 750ms.
19:01:56.01	USH	-	-	750	-	VIS int.time changed from 500ms to 750ms.
19:02:00.79	LSH	-	-	750	-	VIS int.time changed from 500ms to 750ms.
19:02:05.30	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
19:02:05.33	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
19:02:05.34	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
19:02:13.24	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
19:02:13.44	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.

19:02:13.64 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.

Flight:

B298

KEY

- Duff Data
- Minor Problems
- OK
- Not Fitted
- Fitted, Not Operated

Thermometers

- Cabin Temperature:
- Heimann:
- Deiced Temp:
- Non-deiced Temp:

Hygrometers

- FWVS:
- General Eastern:
- Johnson Williams:
- Nevezorov:
- Total Water Probe:

Cameras

- Downward Facing:
- Forward Facing:
- Rearward Facing:
- Upward Facing:

Navigation + Aircraft

- Cruciform GPS:
- GIN Applanix:
- INU Honeywell:
- Radar Altimeter:
- RVSM IAS:
- RVSM Static Pressure:
- XR5 GPS:

Report Created 26/06/2007
15:48:33

Misc Core

- AMTG:
- AVAPS:
- Cabin Pressure:
- Fax machine:
- Printer:
- S9 Static Pressure:
- Satcom C:
- Satcom H:
- Turb Centre-Static:
- Turb Left Right:
- Turb Up-Down:
- Turb Horizontal Chk:
- Turb Vertical Chk:
- Weather Radar:
- DLUs:**
- DLU AERACK:
- DLU BBR Lower:
- DLU BBR Upper:
- DLU Core Chem:
- DLU Core Consoles:
- DLU Port Aft:
- DLU Port Fwd:
- DLU Stbd Fwd:

Radiometers

- Lower:**
- BBR (clear) Lower:
- BBR (IR) Lower:
- BBR (red) Lower:
- Upper:**
- BBR (clear) Upper:
- BBR (IR) Upper:
- BBR (red) Upper:
- ARIES:
- DEIMOS:
- IR Camera:
- JNO2 Lower:
- JNO2 Upper:
- JO1D Lower:
- JO1D Upper:
- MARSS:
- SHIMS Lower:
- SHIMS Upper:
- SWS:
- TAFTS:

Last Updated:

Cloud Probes

- 2DC:
- 2DP:
- FFSSP:
- PCASP:
- ADA:
- CCN:
- CDP:
- CIP 100:
- CIP 25:
- CPI:
- CVI:
- SID1:
- SID2:
- Aerosol**
- CPC 3025A:
- Filters 47mm:
- Filters 90mm:
- Neph - Dry:
- Neph - Wet:
- PSAP:
- AMS:
- CPC 3025 (AMS):
- INC:
- VACC:
- CPC 3010A (CVI):

Chemistry

- CO Aerolaser 5002:
- NOx TE42C:
- Ozone TE49C:
- Ozone TE49:
- SO2 TE43C:
- TDLAS (NIR) CH4:
- TDLAS (NIR) CO2:
- FAGE:
- Formaldehyde:
- NOxy:
- ORAC:
- PAN:
- PERCA:
- Peroxide:
- PTRMS:
- TDLAS (1C):
- WAS Bags:
- WAS Bottles:
- Misc Non-Core**
- CASI/ATM:
- LIDAR:
- LTI:
- SAW Hygrometer:

26/06/2007 11:50:09

Faults / Incidents Log

Flight No. B298

Date: 22 June 2007

Instruments

1. dry neph relative humidity suspect
2. nevz U/S
3. pcasp u/s
4. pcasp 2 u/s

Aircraft

Satcom-H Calls

Post Flight - Turb Probe Water Traps

1. Indicate Amount of Water: a) Nil b) 1-2 drops c) ¼ full or more d) Ice present
2. Emptied by:
3. Dried by:

Fax Transmission Sheet

To: British Honorary Consul Ouagadougou

Attention: Mr P de Lelande

Fax No: #226 50305900

Date: 22 June 2007

Ref:

No. of Pages (incl header): 1

Dear Sir,

As part of a series of Atmospheric Research flights, Directflight hereby request diplomatic clearance and approval for overflight of Burkina Faso including low level flight with a minimum height of 500ft agl and the dropping of radio sondes. The information you require is as follows:

A/C Type:	BAe146-301
Registration:	G-LUXE
Flt Number:	METMAN
Name/Address of Operator:	Directflight Ltd Cranfield Airport Bedford MK43 0AL, UK
Holder of A/C:	British Aerospace Systems
Name/Nationality of Capts:	Capt Alan Foster (British) Capt Alan Roberts (British)
No./Nationality of Crew:	15 (British)
Itinerary:	22/25/28 Jun 07- Depart Nouakchott (GQNN) [1000Z] Land Niamey (DRRN) [1500Z] 21/24/27/29 Jun 07- Depart Niamey [1000Z] Land Nouakchott [1500Z]
Freight:	Nil
Purpose of Flight:	Atmospheric Research

Thank you for your time and attention.

Mike Collins
Flight Operations Manager

*Directflight Operations
Cranfield Airport
Cranfield, Beds
MK43 0AL United Kingdom*

Tel: +44 (0) 1234 754870
Fax: +44 (0) 1234 757649
mike.collins@directflight.co.uk

From: ici [mailto:ici@fasonet.bf]
Sent: 22 June 2007 13:44
To: Mike Collins
Subject: Accord

Dear Mike,

Find your authorisation for flying above Burkina Faso: Accord n° 2007-720/DGACM du 22/06/2007.

Sincerely yours.

Patrick de Lalande
British Honorary Consul
ICI (Initiatives Conseil International)
Tél. : +226 50 30 88 60
L.D. : +226 50 31 25 43
Cell. : +226 70 20 39 82

Burkina Faso overflight clearance granted Accord number 2007 720/DGACM granted to Directflight 22/06/2007.

To cover period of detachment as set out in request to Burkina Faso DGAC through diplomatic channels. Copy of request and reply attached. Permissions for Dropping of Sondes and Low Level Flight to not below 500' agl confirmed as granted by DGAC. Verified verbally with British Honorary Consul in Ouagadougou.

Permission obtained with assistance from British Political Consular, Abidjan, Cote d'Ivoire, Mr Benedict Mann.

Flights may proceed to overfly Burkina Faso on receipt of Flight plan and normal position reporting to Ouagadougou.

Contact details in case of problems – even when airborne:

Mr Patrick de Lelande, British Honorary Consul in Burkina Faso

Mobile: # 226 70 20 39 82

Rgds,

Mike Collins
Flight Operations Manager
Directflight Ltd
Tel #44 (0)1234 757766
Fax #44 (0)1234 758018
mike.collins@directflight.co.uk

New plot, same times

Flight B298 20:18:33

Heading 100 deg Speed 247 knots Height 6.6kft Press 791mb

Lat 13°30.0'N Long 1°42.0'E Wind 4 ms-1/ 0 deg

Temp 19.33C Dewpoint 10.13C

From 17:00 to now

Current values			
---	TIME FROM MIDNIGHT	73113	secs
---	UPPER PYRANOMETER CLEAR FLUX	-14.28	W m-2
---	UPPER PYRANOMETER RED FLUX	21.49	W m-2
---	LOWER PYRANOMETER CLEAR FLUX	19.93	W m-2
---	LOWER PYRANOMETER RED FLUX	7.47	W m-2

New plot, same times

Flight B298 20:17:46

Heading 99 deg Speed 246 knots Height 7.2kft Press 774mb

Lat 13°30.0'N Long 1°36.0'E Wind 5 ms-1/ 1 deg

Temp 17.64C Dewpoint 10.74C

From 17:00 to now

Current values

---	TIME FROM MIDNIGHT	73065	secs
---	UPPER PYRANOMETER CLEAR FLUX	-14.53	W m-2
---	UPPER PYRANOMETER RED FLUX	21.44	W m-2
---	LOWER PYRANOMETER CLEAR FLUX	19.28	W m-2
---	LOWER PYRANOMETER RED FLUX	7.33	W m-2

B298 Images Emailed In Flight

EAA051 MSG dust product 22 Jun 2007 1515 UTC

EAA051_20070622_1515.jpg

EAA041 MSG dust RGB 22 Jun 2007 1515 UTC

EAA041_20070622_1515.jpg

EAAO51 MSG dust product 22 Jun 2007 1615 UTC

EAAO51_20070622_1615.jpg

EAAO41 MSG dust RGB 22 Jun 2007 1630 UTC

EAAO41_200706221630.jpg

EAA051 MSG dust product 22 Jun 2007 1715 UTC

EAA051_20070622_1715.jpg

EAA041 MSG dust RGB 22 Jun 2007 1715 UTC

EAA041_20070622_1715.jpg

EAA051 MSG dust product 22 Jun 2007 1800 UTC

EAA051_20070622_1800.jpg

EAA041 MSG dust RGB 22 Jun 2007 1800 UTC

EAA041_20070622_1800.jpg

EAA051 MSG dust product 22 Jun 2007 1830 UTC

EAA051_20070622_1830.jpg

EAA041 MSG dust RGB 22 Jun 2007 1830 UTC

EAA041_20070622_1830.jpg

EEO41 MSG dat RGB 22 Jun 2007 1930 UTC

EEO41_20070622_1930.jpg

MET9 22 JUN 2007 1800 BNW IR_108 5

SDDI-20070622-1800-BNW-09-IR_108-05-600.jpg

GRADS: COLA/IGES
 -15 -12 -9 -6 -3 0 3 6 9
 up14.5N19.gif 2007-06-22-20:39

GRADS: COLA/IGES
 -10 -8 -6 -4 -2 0 2 4
 vp14.5N19.gif 2007-06-22-20:36

v-component meridional wind at 15N

GrADS: COLA/IGES

vp13N20.gif

2007-06-22-20:19

10m max wind[m/s] and 10m streamlines

GrADS: COLA/IGES

v10max19.gif

2007-06-22-14:16

MISSING LOG SHEETS:

The following log sheets are not available for flight B298:

Log	Reason
Pre-flight log	No log available
Cloud Physics Processing	Processing yet to be completed.
Core Chemistry	no In Flight log except in cases of instrument problems
AVAPS	No sondes dropped
PSAP log	No log as PSAP pump/filter info included on Flight Summary page
Wet Nephelometer	No operator on GERBIL

Document control

Revision	Date	Author	Comments
r0	05 Sep 2007	Doug Anderson	Initial version missing the above noted logs
r1			
r2			

VIDEO RECORDINGS:

2 x Forward Facing Cameras
2 x Downward Facing Cameras

Digital8 video recordings from this flight reside with :

Jim Haywood

Aerosol Research Manager
Met Office
Cordouan 2 W079
FitzRoy Road
Devon
EX1 3PB

Tel: +44 (0) 1392 885510
Fax: +44 (0) 1392 885681

E-mail: jim.haywood@metoffice.gov.uk